

UNDERSTANDING THE ADHESION AT THE INTERFACE IN CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The mechanism of composite interfacial adhesion has been investigated by surveying the literature in order to identify mechanical, physical and chemical known contributions to the bond. With the carbon/epoxy system selected mechanical interlocking is considered irrelevant and surface energy measurements were performed to verify that physical adhesion is not significant. However, the evidence for chemical bonding is presented for electrolytically treated fibres and a correlation is found between resin clamping pressure and a frictional interfacial shear strength for untreated fibres. The latter appear to bond in a mechanical manner and the electrolytic process creates chemical bonding potential.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are strongly dependent on the interface between the two components. Most previous work has concentrated on either strengthening or weakening the interface when in fact a compromise is necessary. It is essential to study the various factors contributing to the bond in order to be able to have control in modifying the adhesion to suit the required property. There are generally three possible adhesion mechanisms and these are mechanical (interlocking) physical (Van der Waals, hydrogen bonds) and chemical (covalent bonds). Many studies have been carried out identifying the various contributing factors. In the first half of this paper some of these will be discussed. They have been divided into fibre and resin dominated properties and subdivided into mechanical, physical and chemical type bonding. After that experimental studies performed to verify some theories will be discussed.

2. ADHESION STUDIES

2.1. Fibre dominated properties

Studies concerning the mechanical versus chemical debate have been mostly carried out by workers who treated fibres to remove 'functionality' and then tested interfacial shear strength of fibres in resin before and after the removal, e.g. Donnet et al. (1). They found

that adhesion of fibres was reduced but not to the level of untreated fibres. Increased surface area encouraging mechanical interlocking was thought to be the remaining factor. In some cases this may have been so (2,3) but Drzal (4) found no correlation with surface area and only a small drop in adhesion of 16% after removing surface groups. He considered that the remaining 84% was due to the removal of a weak defect laden outer layer. Since then evidence of this behaviour of the electrolytic treatment process has been shown by Klinklin and Guigon (5) using TEM and Marshall and Price using STM (6). Some of the above conflicts may have been due to the heat treatment to remove functionality increasing surface area. Also materials, although essentially PAN based high strength or high modulus fibres and epoxy resin were not identical in most cases. Robinson et al. (7) found with XAS fibres (as used in this study) that no significant change in area occurred until 3-4× standard treatment or optimum adhesion so it was assumed that area had no strong effect. It was thus established that interlocking played little part in the bond.

Chemistry and the extent and type of bonding has been investigated by several workers using surface techniques such as XPS (x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) (9,10) and SIMS (11), also titration (12,2) and DSC or IR spectroscopy (13,14). It has been shown that a chemical bond exists and that the bonding is probably via COOH groups on the surface. The third adhesion mechanism, that of physical adhesion, has been assessed by the determination of surface energies. Nardin and Ward (15) found that polyethylene fibres bonded physically to epoxy resin. Kaelble et al. (16) introduced the concept that good adhesion is based on a balance of polar and dispersive components across the interface. Consequently if the resin has equal or lower polar component of surface energy than the fibre then it should wet the fibre. Typical resin polar components are of the order of 10-20 mJm⁻². Typical fibre polar components range from 18-30 mJm⁻² (17). From these values it would appear that the untreated fibre polarity is sufficient.

2.2. Resin dominated properties

In this section we will be considering mechanical, physical and chemical aspects of resin contribution. Physical properties in terms of surface energy were discussed previously. Mechanical aspects cover those associated with interlocking but also resin clamping pressure due to shrinkage and modulus influences on stress transfer assuming a perfect bond as in the Cox model (18).

Mechanical interlocking may be influenced by viscosity and gel time, i.e. whether or not a resin has a low enough viscosity and long enough gel time to penetrate pores on the fibre surface. We can investigate this by use of the Washburn equation (19) which in its simplest form for horizontal capillaries is as follows:

$$x^2 = \frac{R\gamma_{LV}(\cos\theta_e)t}{2\eta}$$

where x is the distance of penetration, R the radius of the capillary, η the viscosity of the fluid, γ^{LV} the surface tension of the liquid, θ_e is the equilibrium contact angle and t is the time taken to penetrate distance x. Taking typical values for which we have available data, HG 9101 resin of 55 mN/m for $\gamma_{LV} \cos \theta$ (20) a viscosity of about 0.1 Pas, a pore radius of 1 nm (21) and a time of penetration (gel time) of 10 min, a value of penetration distance

0.17 μm is calculated. For a resin of lower surface energy, higher contact angle and higher viscosity there may be a problem of pore penetration. For the resin used in this study it was considered that there would not be a problem. Turgut and Sancaktar used viscosity arguments to explain their results in terms of molecular interdiffusion (22).

The resin will shrink during cure due to thermal effects and curing reactions. In a single fibre composite this will mean a clamping pressure will arise and contribute to bond strength. However in a close packed composite a resin pocket between fibres will produce tensile stresses in the resin and across the interface (23). In reality a combination of these phenomena will occur throughout the composite.

Stress transfer may be affected by the stiffness of the adjacent material. The fibre constraint is thought to affect the apparent modulus of the interphase region but also it is believed (5,13,14,24-26) that the ratio of resin/hardener varies in this zone up to several hundred nanometers from the fibre. The modulus alters accordingly and the Cox model (18) predicts a better or worse stress transfer depending on whether it is higher or lower, respectively. Drzal discovered (27) that resin/hardener ratio was not proportional to G_m but had a minimum value. He further (28) carried out a series of experiments to determine the effect of G_m on interfacial shear strength. The results showed that the Cox model could be obeyed. Turgut and Sancaktar (22) believe that sizing improves stress transfer due to a more even stress distribution.

Chemical considerations have been studied by Horie et al. (29) to show fibre/resin interaction using solvent extraction. They found that both hydrogen and covalent bonding occurred. Garton et al. (13,14) showed that there was preferential adsorption of the amine catalyst in anhydride cured resin or amine hardener onto the fibre. Fitzer (30) suggested that the hardener acts as a coupling agent. A few workers have studied the direct interaction of resin with fibres by XPS (31-33).

It is very difficult to identify the resin properties which are responsible for an increase or reduction in shear strength and they are mostly interrelated. In the next section some of the experiments used to verify uncertain details from the literature study are presented. The resin study includes only resin shrinkage as the arguments for viscosity and modulus are conclusive (but more work needs to be carried out on the interphase modulus). Chemical contributions are not definitive but it is well established that the potential for bonding is there if the fibre has sufficient appropriate chemical functionality. Surface energy values are well known for the resin tested (polar $\sim 10 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$) so only fibre surface energy values needed to be determined. Finally it is accepted that mechanical interlocking plays no strong part in the bonding so this will not be further examined.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1. Interface tests

Both fragmentation and pull-out tests were performed on the control resin with untreated fibres and treated fibres. Only fragmentation tests were performed on the untreated and highly treated fibres with control resin and variations.

3.1.1. Pull-out tests

The pull-out tests were conducted using the method developed by Pitkethly and Doble (34). The method is described in detail in ref. (35). Essentially a fibre is embedded in a small pool of resin by means of a fibre guide and cured. The other end of the fibre is attached by solder to a soldering iron fixed to an Instron top grip. Resulting load/displacement plots generate data for initial debond load, maximum debond load and frictional pull-out load with embedded length determined from SEM photography. Analysis of the data follows using Hsueh's model (36,37) to generate maximum interfacial shear strength and Gao et al.'s model (38) to generate fracture toughness. The application of these models to experimental data is discussed in ref. (39) and (35).

3.1.2. Fragmentation tests

These were performed using a standard technique with dogbone single fibre composite samples strained on a microtensometer attached to a microscope until the fibre has completely broken. Analysis of the distribution of lengths using a Kelly/Tyson (40) model adapted by Henstenburg and Phoenix (41) is described in ref. (35) and essentially produces an average shear strength for the interface.

3.2. Materials

PAN based high strength carbon fibres were electrolytically oxidised with ammonium bicarbonate from 0 to 100 Cm^{-2} . The control resin was Ciba Geigy MY750 with hardener HY951 (tetrafunctional amine). They were mixed 100:12 ratio and cured for three hours at 60°C, post cured at 120°C. Three variations were tested: A - post cure increased from 120°C to 150°C; B - increased hardener/resin ratio 100/12 to 100/24; and C - addition of diluent PGE (phenyl glycidyl ether).

Of the above, increased oxidation caused the interfacial shear strengths and fracture toughness to increase up to an optimum 25 Cm^{-2} . The resin variations A and C increased the shear strength with untreated fibre but not treated fibre. No other changes were significant. Values are shown in Table 1.

3.3. Characterisation of fibre and matrix

3.3.1. Measurement of fibre surface energy components

The Wilhelmy plate technique (42) was chosen to determine the surface energy of selected fibres after different levels of treatment. The method is based on the measurement of a force increase on immersion of the fibres in a series of liquids of known surface energy. The method is fully described in ref. (42). Values obtained from these tests are given in Table 1 and indicate that the polar component increases with surface treatment. However, it continues to increase past the optimum treatment level. Figure 1 shows a plot of the total component (polar + dispersive) versus shear strength measured by fragmentation and pull-out tests. There appears to be fairly good correlation up to 25 Cm^{-2} but surface energy continues to increase and shear strength does not past this point. It is unlikely that the physical contribution to the bond is significant as the polar component of even the untreated fibre is well above the resin value. The surface energy may be increasing due to oxygen groups on the surface which do not contribute to a bond. This will be discussed in the following section.

3.3.2. Chemical contributions

XPS (x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) was used to determine the oxygen content of the treated and untreated fibre surfaces. A method using adsorption isotherms was then adopted to determine the level of fibre surface acidity (specifically COOH groups) which would bond to the resin. Both methods are fully described in ref. (10). The second technique involves soaking fibres in increasing concentrations of silver nitrate or magnesium sulphate solutions and measuring the uptake of the positive ion by the COOH groups. Adsorption isotherms are then adopted to interpret the data. Acidity is calculated from the number of COOH groups by a method from ref. (8). The values of acidity thus determined from silver nitrate and magnesium sulphate tests are given in Table 1 and Mg data plotted against the corresponding fibre/resin shear strength in Figure 2 and fracture toughness in Figure 3. Values of oxygen content are also given in Table 1 in C/O ratios. It is now clear that the surface energy could indeed be increasing in proportion to oxygen groups whether these will bond or not. Acidity increases with surface treatment also. Shear strength increases almost linearly with acidity and fracture toughness follows the same trend but is not directly proportional. Unlike surface energy there is no real increase after optimum bond strength level 25 Cm^2 . It may be that the previously proposed idea of removal of a weakly bonded surface layer may occur between 0 and 10 Cm^2 and only after this does the increase in bond strength proportionally follow the increase in acidity. If this is the case then the idea that 16% increase in bond strength is due to chemistry (5) and 84% due to the weak layer removal would agree with these results. It would also fit in with the oxygen content results where a drop is noticed at 10 Cm^2 followed by an increase.

3.3.3. Shrinkage pressure and frictional effects

For this investigation the coefficients of thermal expansion and the Tg for all resins were determined using a dilatometer. Values are given in Table 1. In order to determine the residual clamping pressure on the fibre, q_o , that results from a cooling differential of ΔT the following expression from Butler, et al. (43) was employed.

$$q_o = [E_z(\alpha_m - \alpha_{fz}) + E_r(\alpha_m - \alpha_{fr})] \Delta T \dots \quad (1)$$

where α_m is the thermal expansion coefficient of the matrix and α_{fz} and α_{fr} are respectively the axial and transverse thermal expansion coefficients of the fibre. The effective axial and transverse elastic moduli, E_z and E_r are given by

$$E_z = \frac{E_m k}{\alpha} \dots \quad E_r = \frac{E_z}{\nu} \quad (2)$$

for a low volume fraction system where $\alpha = E_m/E_f$ (Young's modulus of the matrix/Young's modulus of the fibre), $\nu_{m/f}$ is the Poisson's ratio of fibre or matrix and k is defined as

$$k = \frac{\alpha \nu_f}{a(1 - \nu_f) + 1 + \nu_m} \dots \quad (3)$$

E_z and E_r should only be considered to be parameters estimating the contributions of moduli in each direction in the interphase zone. They have been derived from expressions by Vedula et al. (44) solving the stress state in a thick walled cylinder model and converted to the present form by Butler et al. (43). The model assumes an elastically isotropic but thermoelastically anisotropic media. This is in fact not accurate for carbon fibre which is also elastically anisotropic, however, the effect is considered to be negligible and will not be taken into account in the present work. The value of ΔT will be the temperature difference

between the stress free temperature, T_{sf} , and room temperature. In practice T_{sf} is taken to be T_g . To take account of any shrinkage above T_g an adaptation of the above expression is

$$q_o^* = E_z[(\alpha_{m1} - \alpha_{fz}) \Delta T1 + (\alpha_{m2} - \alpha_{fz}) \Delta T2] + E_r[(\alpha_{m1} - \alpha_{fr}) \Delta T1 + (\alpha_{m2} - \alpha_{fr}) \Delta T2] . \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta_{m1/2}$ are the coefficients of thermal expansion above (1) and below (2) the T_g , $\Delta T1/2$ are the cooling differentials 1- from the temperature of post cure in each case to the T_g and 2- from the T_g down to room temperature. Parameters, q_o and q_o^* are given in Table 1 calculated using values of $E_m = 3$ GPa, $E_f = 230$ GPa, $\nu_f = 0.2$, $\nu_m = 0.4$, $\alpha_{fz} = 8$ and $\alpha_{fr} = 0$. The shrinkage stress, q_o (or q_o^*), is related to the interfacial shear strength, τ_i , if frictional stress transfer only is assumed

$$\tau_i = \mu q_o \quad (5)$$

where μ is the coefficient of friction. Figure 4 is a plot of q_o and q_o^* versus fragmentation shear strength with untreated fibre. There is very good correlation and this phenomenon explains the increase in interfacial shear strength for resins A and C with untreated fibre compared to the control resin. B exhibited no increase in shrinkage stress or shear strength from the control. The effect was not the same with treated fibre and it is evident that if there is a chemical bond the mechanical pressure is less significant.

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion the above discussion will be summarised. The previous works on the contributions to adhesion at the interface of electrolytically oxidised PAN based fibres with epoxy resin showed that mechanical interlocking was not important. Results in this paper have further demonstrated that physical contributions are not significant. It was also found that there is a chemical contribution but it may be as little as 16%, the remainder probably being due to the removal of a weakly bonded layer from the surface. Further it would appear that untreated fibres bond in a mechanical manner and are affected by changes in clamping pressure. After treatment the fibres bond chemically and are not affected significantly.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank J F Watts, M G Bader and J E Castle for their contributions to the above work.

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Table 1. Table of results for interface and characterisation studies.

Fibre surface treatment (C/m ²)	Surface energy (mJ/m ²) Polar, total	Surface C/O ratio	Acidity (→eq/g) AgNO ₃ , MgSO ₄	Resin type	Tg (°C)	α, α ₂ < Tg, > Tg (°C ⁻¹ 10 ⁻⁶)	q ₀ , q ₀ (MPa)	Interfacial shear strength Pull-out, Fragment (MPa)	Interfacial Fracture Toughness (Jm ⁻²)
0	30.1, 48.6	23.0	5.9 6.4	Control	108	37 95	7.5, 10.3	43.0 14.1	7.3
0				A	134	30 90	9.9, 15.1	23.1	
0				B	110	36 86	8.3, 10.6	15.6	
0				C	110	45 100	9.9, 12.5	14.1	
5		10.9		Control				40.0	
10	35.4, 53.9	10.1	8.9	Control				53.0 32.2	22.2
25	39.4, 57.9	11.0	15.9 15.0	Control				66.0 62.2	24.8
50		10.5		Control				66.0 52.4	24.5
100	47.5, 66.0	8.2	15.1 17.2	Control				66.0 65.5	24.8

Figure 1. Total surface energy of carbon fibre versus interfacial shear strength + pull-out □ fragmentation

Figure 2. Acidity of fibre surface versus interfacial shear strength + pull-out □ fragmentation

Figure 3. Acidity of fibre surface versus debond fracture toughness (pull-out) of interface

Figure 4. Clamping pressure of resin versus interfacial shear strength (fragmentation) □ below Tg * shrinkage all T